

Enhanced hydrogen peroxide production and organic pollutants degradation using P-doped carbon nitride photocatalysts

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of phosphorus (P) doping onto the structural, optical, and photocatalytic properties of graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄). g-C₃N₄ materials doped with different amounts of P were synthesized to identify the optimal phosphorus loading for enhancing photocatalytic degradation of carbamazepine (CBZ), a highly persistent contaminant, while simultaneously improving hydrogen peroxide production. Structural and morphological analyses showed that all materials preserved the g-C₃N₄ structure, although crystallinity decreased with increasing P content. More defined melem-related characteristics and better structural order were present at low and moderate doping levels (5–17.5 mmol), whereas no significant morphological differences were observed. The band gap increased slightly at high phosphorus loadings (>30 mmol), suggesting modifications of electronic transitions induced by a massive dopant presence. These changes affected photocatalytic behaviour: CBZ degradation was slow under visible light, but greatly enhanced under UV-A irradiation, with P(5)C₃N₄ showing the highest activity. Higher phosphorus loadings led to reduced performance, consistent with reduced crystallinity and melem species. H₂O₂ production increased with phosphorus content and was further promoted in the presence of CBZ, acting as a sacrificial agent. A general inverse relationship emerged between maximum H₂O₂ levels and CBZ degradation efficiency, except for P(5)C₃N₄, which retained the best performance in both processes. To further elucidate the photocatalytic mechanisms, ten transformation products were identified including mono- and di-hydroxylated derivatives and acridinic species. Finally, P(5)C₃N₄ maintained good CBZ removal efficiency in two actual water matrices, wastewater effluent and aquaculture water, so proving material's applicability under environmentally relevant conditions.

1. Introduction

Water pollution remains one of the most critical global environmental issues, exacerbated by intensified human, industrial, and agricultural activities, as well as rapid urbanization and population growth [1–3]. The increasing scarcity of freshwater further highlights the urgent need of advancing wastewater treatment technologies. In particular, the removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), a class that includes pharmaceuticals, pesticides, industrial chemicals, and endocrine-disrupting compounds, poses significant challenges due to their persistence, low biodegradability, and potential for bioaccumulation [4–7].

Among the most promising technologies for addressing these pollutants are advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), which rely on the in-situ generation of highly reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), superoxide anions (O_2^-), singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), ozone (O_3), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) [8–12]. These species can degrade a wide range of organic pollutants into less harmful products, such as CO_2 and H_2O .

In recent years, graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) has emerged as a highly promising metal-free photocatalyst for environmental applications, owing to its unique electronic and structural properties [13–15]. Firstly, synthesized by Liebig in 1834, g-C₃N₄ features a tri-s-triazine polymeric framework. Its moderate band gap (~2.7 eV) enables

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absorption in the visible region, making it highly attractive for solar-driven photocatalytic processes [16,17].

One of the most relevant applications of g-C₃N₄ is the photocatalytic production of hydrogen peroxide [18–20]. Conventional H₂O₂ production through the anthraquinone auto-oxidation process raises environmental concerns; therefore, finding a more sustainable way to generate H₂O₂ for promoting AOPs is crucial. H₂O₂ generation by g-C₃N₄ can proceed via two primary pathways: the two-electron oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) and the two-electron water oxidation reaction (WOR). Nonetheless, ORR and WOR can proceed with other mechanisms, namely one-, or four-electron, associated with different reduction potentials and reaction products [21]. The relevant half-reactions are as follows:

One-electron ORR:

Two-electron ORR (preferred for H₂O₂ generation):

Four-electron ORR (complete reduction to water):

One-electron WOR (H₂O oxidation to HO radical):

Two-electron WOR (H₂O oxidation to H₂O₂):

Four-electron WOR (H₂O oxidation to O₂):

Among these, the two-electron ORR (Eq. 2) is particularly advantageous due to its relatively low thermodynamic potential (0.695 V vs. NHE), compared with the one-electron ORR, while the four-electron reduction to water is usually slow, because of the simultaneous transfer of four electrons and four protons and the molecular rearrangement needed to cleave the O-O bond [19,21]. In contrast, the two-electron WOR (Eq. 5), although feasible under light irradiation, is less favourable due to its high potential (1.763 V vs. NHE) and carries an increased risk of H₂O₂ decomposition, especially in the presence of catalytic active sites.

Despite these promising advantages, pristine g-C₃N₄ suffers from limitations, including rapid charge recombination, low quantum efficiency, and suboptimal selectivity for the two-electron ORR [17,19]. To overcome these issues, various modification strategies have been developed. Among them phosphorus doping has shown the potential for improving both the charge separation and the catalytic selectivity for H₂O₂ production [22–24].

Phosphorus doping introduces heteroatoms into the carbon nitride framework, which can improve the lifetime of the photogenerated charge carriers enhancing electronic conductivity. These effects promote more efficient separation and migration of photogenerated charge carriers, thereby facilitating ROS production and improving pollutant degradation. Additionally, P-doping can tailor the electronic structure of g-C₃N₄ to favour the two-electron ORR pathway, thus increasing selectivity toward H₂O₂ formation [17].

In this study, we investigated the influence of phosphorus content on the photocatalytic performance of g-C₃N₄. A series of P-doped g-C₃N₄ materials were synthesized with varying dopant concentrations using

melamine and ammonium dihydrogen phosphate as precursors.

Their structural and optical properties, as well as their photocatalytic performances, were evaluated not only in terms of hydrogen peroxide production, but also with respect to the degradation of CBZ, selected for its high environmental persistence. To extend the relevance of the study to real environmental scenarios, the phosphorus-modified material showing the most promising behaviour in both H₂O₂ formation and CBZ removal has been further examined in actual water matrices, such as effluent wastewater and fish-farm water. These tests are intended to gain insight into the influence of real water composition on reactive species dynamics and overall photocatalytic response, and to assess the robustness of the photocatalysts under realistic operating conditions. Furthermore, the material with the highest production of hydrogen peroxide formation will be subjected to UVC irradiation to explore whether in situ photolysis of the generated peroxide can further promote CBZ degradation, offering additional insight into potential process intensification strategies.

2. Materials and Method

2.1. Reagents

Melamine (purity 99%), carbamazepine (purity ≥ 98%), ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (purity ≥ 99.0%), 4-aminoantipyrine (reagent grade), horseradish peroxidase and hydrogen peroxide 30% (w/w) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Merck Life Science S.r.l, Milan, Italy); ethanol, acetonitrile, methanol, orthophosphoric acid 85% and sulfuric acid 95% from VWR International S.r.l. (Milan, Italy).

2.2. Synthesis of Materials

P-doped g-C₃N₄ was synthesized following a previously reported procedure [25] and named as P(x) C₃N₄, where x indicates the amount of phosphorus precursor in mmol (x = 5, 10, 17.5, 25, 30, 50), corresponding to melamine/NH₄H₂PO₄ (w/w) mass ratios of 17.4, 8.4, 5.0, 3.5, 2.9, and 1.7, respectively. The investigated range started from 5 mmol because previous studies on phosphorus-modified g-C₃N₄ reported lower photocatalytic activity at lower precursor concentrations [26]. Higher precursor amounts were then selected in order to examine the effect of progressively increasing phosphorus loading over a broad compositional range. The necessary amount of NH₄H₂PO₄ was added to an aqueous suspension of melamine (10 g) and stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The resulting mixture was then dried in a ventilated oven at 50 °C for 2–3 days to remove water. Finally, the powder was calcined in a tubular furnace under nitrogen flow with a ramp of 3 °C/min up to 520 °C, followed by a 2-hour dwell at that temperature.

2.3. Characterization of the catalysts

The crystalline phases of the synthesized photocatalysts were characterized by a powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) instrument (PANalytical PW3040/60-X'Pert PRO MPD, Netherlands) with CuKα (λ=1.5418 Å) radiation (cathode voltage: 45 kV, current: 40 mA). UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-DRS) was performed using a UV/VIS/NIR spectrometer Varian Cary 5000 (Agilent). Photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy was acquired using a FP-8500 spectrofluorometer (JASCO Corporation, Japan). Morphological analyses were performed with a FEG-SEM TESCAN model S9000G, equipped with a Schottky-type FEG source and a theoretical resolution of 0.7 nm in In-Beam SE (Ultra High Resolution) mode at 15 keV. Point microanalysis and elemental distribution maps were obtained with an energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) for X-ray microanalysis, with an OXFORD EDS Ultim Max detector and AZTEC Software. The samples were mounted on specially designed aluminium stubs pre-coated with double-sided conductive carbon tape to ensure optimal electrical conductivity. Subsequently, a thin chromium layer (~5 nm) was deposited onto the samples by metallization to

further enhance surface conductivity for electron microscopy analysis.

BET surface area was measured by N_2 adsorption at 77 K on a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 apparatus. Prior to the measurements, the samples were degassed under vacuum (residual pressure $\sim 10^{-2}$ mbar) at 80 °C for several hours to remove adsorbed atmospheric contaminants from the surface and pores. Degassing was considered complete once stable vacuum conditions were maintained under static mode.

2.4. Irradiation tests

All the synthesized photocatalysts were tested for the hydrogen peroxide production and substrate degradation, using a catalyst concentration of 2 g/L. Milli-Q water was used as medium and the suspensions were irradiated in a Solarbox (CO.FO.MEGRA Milan, Italy) equipped with a Xenon lamp and a cut off filter at 340 nm. The UVC irradiation was performed by a lamp Puritec, 9 W with an irradiance of $\cong 44 \text{ W/m}^2$ (emission maximum at 254 nm). The concentration of produced hydrogen peroxide was determined using the horseradish peroxidase-coupled oxidations method described by Frew et al. [27] and a Cary 100 Scan UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Agilent).

The degradation experiments were performed on a solution (MilliQ water and actual aqueous samples) of carbamazepine at 10 mg/L at natural pH (pH = 7.1). Experiments were carried on in closed Pyrex glass cells kept under magnetic stirring and filled with 5 mL of sample and catalyst suspension. At fixed time intervals, the cells were removed from irradiation, the samples were subsequently filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE membrane and the photodegradation process was monitored over time by HPLC-UV. Analyses were performed with a Merck-Hitachi HPLC system equipped with a I-4200 UV-VIS detector and a Lichrospher 100 RP C18 column (125 \times 4 mm, 5 μm). The detection wavelength was set at 285 nm eluting with 65% of phosphoric acid solution at pH 2.8 and 35% of acetonitrile at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. The retention time for carbamazepine was 5.8 min. To clarify the main pathway of H_2O_2 formation, control experiments were carried out using the $P(5)C_3N_4$ catalyst (2 g/L) and 10 ppm CBZ under different atmospheric conditions: ambient air (no bubbling), oxygen saturation (15 min O_2 bubbling at a flow rate of 100 mL min^{-1}), and anoxic conditions (15 min N_2 purging at a flow rate of 100 mL min^{-1}).

Adsorption tests were performed keeping the samples containing carbamazepine and photocatalysts in the dark for six hours.

To assess photocatalytic activity in real matrices, two different water matrices were employed and spiked with CBZ (final concentration 10 ppm): a wastewater effluent (WWE) and water collected from a fish farm (Levaldigi, FFW). The main chemical parameters of the matrices are reported in Table S1.

Spin-trapping experiments were carried out using a X-band benchtop EPR spectrometer (ADANI's SPINSCAN X) and DMPO (5,5-Dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide, Sigma Aldrich) was employed for hydroxyl radical detection.

Experimental conditions: 0.5 mL of aqueous solution containing DMPO 0.044 mM, not buffered, 10 mg of catalyst, 1 ppm of CBZ solution and H_2O_2 155 μM , irradiated with UVC lamp.

2.5. LC-MS/MS analysis of transformation products

To further investigate the formation of transformation products (TPs), additional experiments were carried out using the most efficient photocatalyst, $P(5)C_3N_4$. Chromatographic separation was performed on a Shimadzu® Prominence UFLC system coupled to an Sciex® 3200 Q TRAP triple quadrupole equipped with an ESI ionization source and a Synergi® 4 μm Fusion-RP 80 Å column (100 \times 2 mm). The mobile phases consisted of water with 0.1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid (B). A gradient elution was applied as follows: 5% B from 0.0 to 3.50 min, 20% B at 8.50 min, 60% B at 14.50 min, and 98% B from 16.00 to 16.50 min, followed by a return to 5% B at 17.00 min for column re-equilibration. The flow rate was kept at 0.25 mL min^{-1} until

17.00 min and then increased to 0.50 mL min^{-1} . The total run time was 22 min. The column temperature was maintained at 40 °C and the injection volume was 50 μL . Full-scan data acquisition was performed in positive ESI mode using the Enhanced MS experiment. The scan range was m/z 100–350. The declustering potential and entrance potential were set to 50 V and 10 V, respectively. Curtain gas was set at 35 psi, ion spray voltage at 5500 V, and GS1/GS2 at 45 and 55 psi, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Morphological and structural characterization

XRD measurements were used to initially investigate the crystalline structures of synthesized materials (Fig. 1, Table 1). XRD patterns of all samples revealed two peculiar peaks at about 27.3° and 13.3°, related to the interlayer stacking (002) and the inner planar structure packing (100) of tri-s-triazine units [28], respectively. As reported in a previous work [25], these two reflexes proved the presence of graphitic C_3N_4 phase, confirming that the precursors are entirely condensed, without crystalline phosphate impurities. The degree of crystallinity decreased with P-doping; at the highest doping level, $P(50)C_3N_4$, the material was found to have low crystallinity.

The observed decrease in crystallinity with increasing phosphorus content can be attributed to the influence of P incorporation on the condensation process of g- C_3N_4 . During thermal polymerization of melamine, the formation of an ordered graphitic structure relies on the progressive condensation of tri-s-triazine units into extended planar networks. The introduction of phosphorus species can interfere with this process by forming P-N and/or P-C linkages, which alter the local bonding environment and hinder the regular growth of polymeric domains.

Moreover, due to its larger atomic radius and different valence compared to carbon and nitrogen, phosphorus incorporation induces lattice distortions and structural defects within the g- C_3N_4 framework. These effects become more pronounced at higher dopant loadings, leading to reduced long-range stacking order along the (002) direction and partial suppression of ordered melem/polymeric structures. As a result, smaller and more disordered crystallites are formed, which is reflected in the broadening and attenuation of XRD peaks observed at high P contents.

The position of the main peak referred to the (002) plane at 27° remains substantially unchanged with the doping level, witnessing that the distance between the tri-s-triazine planes does not change with the P concentration. The $P(50)C_3N_4$ material is the only exception. $P(50)C_3N_4$ is the least crystalline among the materials synthesized and also the one with the largest distance among the tri-s-triazine planes. The same reasoning holds for the peak referred to the plane (100) at $2\theta \approx 13.2^\circ$, which position does not significantly change with P doping level. Nevertheless, this peak shows two maxima: the peak at lower 2θ , approximately 12.5°, can be assigned to melem oligomers [29], while the second at larger 2θ , approximately 13.3°, at polymeric g- C_3N_4 . This melem signature is visible for all P-doping levels, with the exception of P(50), for which no peak at lower 2θ values could be revealed, also because of the very large signal centered at $2\theta = 26.2^\circ$. The materials at low doping levels, from P(5) to P(17.5), show an additional signal at $2\theta = 25.3^\circ$, which can also be attributed to melem. Therefore, the samples with lower P doping are characterized by the presence of melem oligomers and better crystallinity, while at larger doping levels melem signals are less intense and the materials display less crystalline order.

To investigate the morphology of the samples, analyses were performed via FESEM, and the obtained images are shown in the Fig. 2.

The morphology of the P-doped g- C_3N_4 materials shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. S1 does not exhibit significant change with doping. All the materials consist of aggregates or agglomerates ranging in size from approximately 10–200 μm . At higher magnification, smaller fragments and primary particles are observed, typically exceeding 5–10 μm in size.

Fig. 1. XRD diffractogram of C_3N_4 samples doped with different amount of P.

Table 1

Measured angles of the two characterizing peaks for each P-doped material.

Material	2θ (100)	2θ (002)
P(5) C_3N_4	13.2 / 12.5 ^(a)	27.1 / 25.3 ^(c)
P(10) C_3N_4	13.4 / 12.6 ^(a)	27.3 / 25.3 ^(c)
P(17.5) C_3N_4	13.4 / 12.8 ^(a)	27.2 / 25.3 ^(c)
P(25) C_3N_4	13.2 / 12.8 ^(a)	27.4
P(30) C_3N_4	n.d. ^(b) / 12.8 ^(a)	27.2
P(50) C_3N_4	n.d. ^(b)	26.2

(a) Melem, (b) Not detected, (c) Shoulder.

Moreover, these particles show very large pores, well above the 50 nm threshold to be considered macropores, which were probably generated during the thermal treatment following melamine sublimation and

deamination [30].

BET analysis revealed similar and relatively low surface areas for all P(x) C_3N_4 samples ($7\text{--}10\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$), indicating that the macropores observed by FESEM do not significantly affect the accessible specific surface area. Therefore, any differences in catalytic activity among the samples are more likely related to P-induced structural and electronic effects than to morphological variations or differences in accessible surface area.

Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) and Element Mapping Analyses were utilized to provide additional confirmation of the compositions and the spatial distribution of elements in the materials.

The results reveal that the materials were composed mainly by C and N with a small percentage of oxygen, which can be ascribed to environmental contamination or residual phosphate employed as P

Fig. 2. FESEM micrographs, of P(5) C_3N_4 (a); P(10) C_3N_4 (b); P(17.5) C_3N_4 (c); P(25) C_3N_4 (d); P(30) C_3N_4 (e) and P(50) C_3N_4 (f).

precursor. C/N ratios are also larger than expected, as they should be comprised between 0.5, the value of the melamine precursor, and 0.75 characteristic of stoichiometric C_3N_4 . This discrepancy could be ascribed to carbon overestimation due to the nature of the sample support employed. The data also show the presence of P uniformly distributed over the entire surface of the material, indicating the successful incorporation of P into the structure of C_3N_4 . Moreover, for doping levels above 10 mmol of P, the observed O/P ratio is 1.5 or lower, while for phosphate contamination the value of 4 would be expected. At lower P doping phosphate presence cannot be ruled out, nevertheless in that case the large O/P ratio can be explained in terms of lower P content and almost constant O contamination in all the samples. Fig. S2 presents the EDS elemental maps and corresponding spectra for all synthesized materials, while Table 2 reports the elemental composition of the $P(x)C_3N_4$ samples.

3.2. Charge transfer and optical properties

DR-UV-Vis analysis was used to determine the optical band gaps of the materials, by applying the Tauc plot method (Table 3, Fig. S3 A, B). The band gap energy E_g was evaluated using Eq. (7), which relates the optical absorption coefficient α to the photon energy $h\nu$ in semiconductors: [31]

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = A (h\nu - E_g) \quad (7)$$

where A is a proportionality constant and $n = 2$ for direct allowed transitions, while $n = 1/2$ corresponds to indirect allowed transitions. In the Tauc plot, $(\alpha h\nu)^n$ is plotted as a function of $h\nu$, and E_g is obtained by the linear extrapolation of the absorption edge to $(\alpha h\nu)^n = 0$. The absorption coefficient α was derived from the reflectance data using the Kubelka-Munk function $F(R_\infty)$ [32,33].

Since the nature of the electronic transition cannot be known a priori, an incorrect choice of n may affect the calculated band gap (Table 3). Photoluminescence measurements were therefore performed to clarify the nature of the transition. The intense PL emission observed for all samples, particularly for $P(5)C_3N_4$ (Fig. 3), indicates a direct band-gap semiconductor behaviour [34]. Samples $P(30)C_3N_4$ and $P(50)C_3N_4$ also show a blue shift in the emission, consistent with an increased band gap.

Further confirmation of the direct band-gap character comes from the Tauc plots (Fig. S3 A, B): extrapolations using $n = 1/2$ and $n = 2$ yield very similar E_g values, within the experimental uncertainty of 0.1–0.2 eV. In materials with indirect band gaps, the extrapolation with $n = 1/2$ would instead give significantly lower E_g values than the one obtained with $n = 2$. The agreement between the band gaps derived from reflectance and PL, again within the experimental uncertainty of 0.1–0.2 eV, also supports the consistency of this interpretation.

Materials with low phosphorus doping levels exhibit band gap values identical to pristine g- C_3N_4 (2.7 eV), as reported in the literature [17]. A slight increase in band gap is observed when the phosphorus content in the synthesis exceeds 30 mmol.

Table 2

Elemental composition of $P(x)C_3N_4$ materials derived from EDS. Errors are expressed as one standard deviation.

Material	C (at%)	N (at%)	O (at%)	P (at%)	C/N	O/P
$P(5)C_3N_4$	41 ± 3	53 ± 5	6 ± 3	0.5 ± 0.1	0.78	13.4
$P(10)C_3N_4$	54 ± 4	30 ± 3	14.7 ± 0.9	1.2 ± 0.2	1.80	12.7
$P(17.5)C_3N_4$	39 ± 7	49 ± 14	7 ± 4	4.9 ± 2.5	0.79	1.44
$P(25)C_3N_4$	32 ± 15	40 ± 4	17 ± 7	11 ± 5	0.81	1.55
$P(30)C_3N_4$	35 ± 4	42 ± 3	12 ± 2	9.5 ± 1.5	0.84	1.29
$P(50)C_3N_4$	41 ± 19	37 ± 17	13 ± 1	9.4 ± 2.9	1.10	1.35

Table 3

Band gaps of the synthesized materials.

Material	Indirect Band gap (eV)	Direct Band gap (eV) ^(a)	Direct Band gap (eV) ^(b)
$P(5)C_3N_4$	2.74	2.91	2.70
$P(10)C_3N_4$	2.74	2.93	2.69
$P(17.5)C_3N_4$	2.77	2.94	2.69
C_3N_4			
$P(25)C_3N_4$	2.78	3.00	2.71
$P(30)C_3N_4$	2.81	3.04	2.75
$P(50)C_3N_4$	2.89	3.13	2.80

(a) Obtained by Tauc plot and (b) by photoluminescence

Fig. 3. Photoluminescence of the synthesized materials.

3.3. Photocatalytic performance

Preliminary experiments demonstrated that carbamazepine (CBZ) does not undergo photolysis under the investigated irradiation conditions, and that dark adsorption was negligible over the examined time interval (3 h). Under visible-light irradiation ($\lambda > 420$ nm), all materials exhibited limited photocatalytic activity, achieving only about 10–15% removal of the initial CBZ concentration by the end of the investigated time window. In contrast, a significantly enhanced photocatalytic response was observed under UV irradiation ($\lambda > 340$ nm). Assuming that the substrate abatement kinetics follows a pseudo-first-order law (see Fig. S4), the corresponding rate constants were calculated and reported in the Table 4. Under UV-light, the highest degradation efficiency was achieved with $P(5)C_3N_4$, which exhibited a rate constant (k) of $1.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$. This was followed by $P(17.5)C_3N_4$ and $P(10)C_3N_4$, with k values of $1.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ and $9.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively. The data suggest a general negative correlation between increasing phosphorus content and photodegradation efficiency as the materials with higher P loading exhibited lower rate constant, ranging from

Table 4

Kinetic constants of CBZ degradation by investigated materials ([catalyst] = 2.0 g L⁻¹, [CBZ] = 10 ppm, UV-light with $\lambda > 340$ nm).

Material	k (min ⁻¹)
$P(5)C_3N_4$	1.8×10^{-2}
$P(10)C_3N_4$	9.1×10^{-3}
$P(17.5)C_3N_4$	1.1×10^{-2}
$P(25)C_3N_4$	3.2×10^{-3}
$P(30)C_3N_4$	2.4×10^{-3}
$P(50)C_3N_4$	3.5×10^{-3}

$3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ to $2.44 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$. A similar trend was also reported previously for the degradation of 2,4-dichlorophenol and methylene blue using graphitic carbon nitride doped with melamine phosphate [24]. Each test was replicated 2–3 times, yielding a percentage standard deviation between 5% and 7%. The materials can be divided into two groups depending on photocatalytic activity: doping levels between 5 and 17.5 showed better activity than materials with doping levels between 20 and 50. Coherently with previous reports [35], the material where melam was detected through XRD are those with the best photocatalytic performance.

3.4. Hydrogen peroxide production

As a preliminary assessment, the synthesized materials were tested for hydrogen peroxide production in the absence of carbamazepine under illumination at wavelengths $\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda > 340 \text{ nm}$. The maximum H_2O_2 concentrations achieved under each irradiation condition are presented in Fig. 4. As can be observed, the use of shorter wavelengths significantly enhances H_2O_2 production, matching the increased light absorption in the UV portion of the spectrum (Fig. S3). The maximum concentration obtained under UV-Vis irradiation with $\lambda > 340$ increases with P doping level, from $16 \mu\text{M}$ in the presence of $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ to $118 \mu\text{M}$ for $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$.

Under visible-light irradiation, no clear correlation was observed between phosphorus content and H_2O_2 generation. However, under UV light, a positive trend was evident: higher phosphorus doping levels led to increased H_2O_2 concentrations in solution. This suggests that phosphorus incorporation enhances photocatalytic efficiency under higher-energy irradiation.

Regarding the time evolution of H_2O_2 , Fig. S5 (A) shows that under visible light the concentration of hydrogen peroxide increased during the treatment; however, after 2 h, a decline was observed, which was significantly more pronounced for materials with lower phosphorus content. This behaviour is likely due to the depletion of dissolved oxygen in the reaction medium, after which hydrogen peroxide production yield decreases, as molecular oxygen must then be generated via water oxidation (Eq. 6). Therefore, the materials with lower phosphorus content are assumed to exhibit reduced efficiency in the reaction of photogenerated holes with water to produce molecular oxygen, subsequently involved in Eq. 2 to generate hydrogen peroxide.

Under UV light ($\lambda > 340 \text{ nm}$, see Fig. S5 (B)) conversely, materials with higher phosphorus content displayed a more evident bell-shaped

curves, with peak H_2O_2 concentrations typically reached at 2 h. An exception was observed for $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, which showed a further increase in H_2O_2 production after 3 h. At high concentrations, the occurrence of competitive hydrogen peroxide decomposition reactions can be invoked, which may reduce the overall H_2O_2 production efficiency; however, these reactions appear to be less significant for the material with the highest phosphorus content.

By adding CBZ, the H_2O_2 production under irradiation $> 340 \text{ nm}$ increased significantly (Fig. 5, solid bars) for all the investigated materials. This enhancement was particularly pronounced in materials with lower phosphorus content, particularly $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, where the concentration of H_2O_2 increased by a factor of 10 compared to the CBZ-free system.

Unlike in the absence of the sacrificial agent (CBZ), under these experimental conditions no clear correlation could be established between phosphorus content and H_2O_2 production. The best performance was observed with $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, followed by $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, with concentrations of $154.9 \mu\text{M}$ and $131.3 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. In contrast, an inverse relationship seems to link the maximum amount of H_2O_2 produced and degradation rate (dashed line in Fig. 5) for the different investigated materials: lower H_2O_2 concentration in the system generally corresponded to a higher degradation efficiency. Notably, $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ exhibited an anomalous behaviour compared to the other samples, achieving the best performance when both H_2O_2 production and CBZ degradation were considered simultaneously. This phenomenon can be explained by assuming that CBZ acts as a sacrificial agent, reacting specifically with photogenerated holes [25] thereby reducing hole-electron recombination. Therefore, we can infer that the materials with lower P doping levels are characterized by more efficient hole transfer, while at higher doping levels electron transfer kinetics improve. In the absence of CBZ as hole scavenger, photoelectrons can either react with molecular oxygen to give hydrogen peroxide or recombine with photogenerated holes. With CBZ photohole density decrease, because they can be transferred to oxidize CBZ, and H_2O_2 production improves. This improvement becomes more important for the materials that can oxidize better CBZ, namely the materials with lower P doping.

By monitoring H_2O_2 production during the process, a gradual increase ($\text{P}(25)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ and $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, or the attainment of a plateau ($\text{P}(10)$, (17.5) , $(30) \text{C}_3\text{N}_4$) was observed for all materials, with the exception of $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, where the H_2O_2 concentration reached a maximum after 1 h and then decreased (Fig. S6). In this case, it can be assumed that the accumulation of high H_2O_2 concentration in the system, as observed for $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, may promote competitive reactions that consume H_2O_2 .

To clarify the main pathway of H_2O_2 formation, control experiments were carried out using $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ in the presence of CBZ on $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ under different atmospheric conditions (ambient air, O_2 saturation, and N_2 purging). As shown in Fig. S7, the removal of dissolved oxygen by N_2 purging strongly suppressed H_2O_2 production, with the concentration decreasing from $157 \mu\text{M}$ under ambient air to $41 \mu\text{M}$ after 60 min of irradiation. This marked reduction confirms that H_2O_2 is predominantly formed through the two-electron oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) driven by photogenerated electrons, rather than through water oxidation pathways. O_2 saturation did not significantly change the initial H_2O_2 concentration at 60 min ($158 \mu\text{M}$ vs $157 \mu\text{M}$ under ambient air), but it prolonged H_2O_2 accumulation, leading to a higher maximum concentration of $176 \mu\text{M}$ after 120 min. In contrast, under ambient air the H_2O_2 concentration decreased after the first hour, reaching $131 \mu\text{M}$ at 120 min. This behaviour indicates that, in the closed reaction vessel, the gradual depletion of dissolved oxygen limits H_2O_2 production and favours its simultaneous decomposition.

To evaluate the stability of the best-performing material, $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ was tested over three consecutive photocatalytic cycles (180 min each) under UV irradiation ($> 340 \text{ nm}$), monitoring both CBZ degradation and H_2O_2 production (Fig. S8). The material showed very good reusability in terms of CBZ removal, with degradation efficiencies consistently above 94% in all runs. A moderate decrease in H_2O_2 production was observed

Fig. 4. Maximum production of H_2O_2 in the presence of investigated materials under irradiation with $\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda > 340 \text{ nm}$. The bar errors represent the standard deviation of three replicates.

Fig. 5. Bars indicate the maximum production of H₂O₂ in absence (empty bars) and in presence (filled bars) of CBZ 10 ppm. The dashed line reports *k* of CBZ abatement (irradiation with $\lambda > 340$ nm).

after the first cycle, as the maximum concentration at 60 min decreased from 157 μM in the first run to 136 μM and 127 μM in the second and third runs, respectively, after which the trend became more stable. Overall, these results suggest that the catalyst preserves its photocatalytic activity to a large extent over repeated use.

These promising preliminary findings support the development and optimization of photocatalysts for potential use in Fenton-like systems or in synergy with peroxidase enzymes to improve degradation efficiency.

3.5. Formation and evolution of TPs

Under irradiation in the presence of P(5)C₃N₄ photocatalyst, ten transformation products of CBZ were identified (see Table S2 and Fig. 6) and monitored throughout the degradation process (see Fig. S9). The signal at *m/z* 253 can be attributed to the monohydroxylated derivative, for which the presence of the fragment at *m/z* 236 in the MS² spectrum at lower CE (10 eV), consistent with the loss of NH₃, rules out hydroxylation on the amino group. The most favourable hydroxylation sites on the aromatic ring are positions 10 and 11, followed by positions 3 and 7. The high Fukui index values at all these positions indicate that they are susceptible to radical attack. The involvement of position 6 can most

likely be excluded, since the loss of ammonia occurs through hydrogen abstraction from the α -carbon followed by cyclization. The transformation product at *m/z* 251, formed through hydroxylation/oxidation, does not show the neutral loss of 17 amu corresponding to NH₃ [36]. This absence, together with the features observed in the mass spectrum, supports the structural formula shown in the Fig. 6, which is characterized by a ring contraction and an intramolecular cyclization, in agreement with previous studies [37]. However, based on the elements obtained, it is not entirely possible to definitively exclude the structure that retains the seven-carbon central ring characteristic of the parent CBZ molecule. The formation of five dihydroxylated/oxidated products consistent with the signal at *m/z* 267 were observed (TP 267 A, B, C, D, E). The characteristic fragments (*m/z* 249 and 221) present in MS² spectrum for TP 267B, already found during photocatalyzed processes, can justify the structural formula shown in the Fig. 6. For the other isobaric products, no useful information is available to identify the positions involved in the hydroxylation and oxidation reactions. The TP 224 that shows the fragment at *m/z* 196 in MS² suggests the formation of hydroxy acridine-9-carbaldehyde arising likely from the detachment of isocyanic acid and hydroxylation of TP 251. The detection of the product with *m/z* 196, characterized by CO loss, supports the formation of acridine-aldehyde and acridone-like structures, respectively. Acridine

Fig. 6. Proposed degradation pathway of CBZ.

(m/z 180) appeared rapidly but decreased earlier than the other species, suggesting its further transformation or mineralization rather than accumulation. These structures, supported by characteristic neutral losses (NH_3 , HNCO , CO) and retention time trends, are consistent with CBZ degradation acridinic pathway reported for semiconductor-based AOPs [38].

3.6. Effect of real matrices

To test the photocatalytic performance in treating real matrices, the most efficient material in terms of degradation and production of H_2O_2 , $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$, was also used to abate CBZ in a wastewater effluent sample (WWE) and in water sampled in a fish farm (Levaldigi, FFW). Testing the photocatalytic material in actual water is crucial to assess its behaviour under realistic environmental conditions, since real matrices typically contain various inorganic ions and natural organic matter that can interfere with the photocatalytic process. These components may compete with the target pollutants for active sites, absorb incident light, or modify the surface charge and pH of the system, influencing the generation of reactive species and the overall degradation efficiency [39]. However, these effects depend on the specific nature and composition of DOC. Although a reduction in the degradation rate is observed (insert Fig. 7), especially in fish farm water (FFW), likely due to its greater matrix complexity, the photocatalytic treatment completely removed CBZ, confirming the robustness of the materials under realistic conditions. In the case of FFW, the lower dissolved organic carbon (DOC) content in respect to wastewater effluent (WWE) suggests that the reduced degradation efficiency may be linked both to differences in DOC composition and to the higher concentration of inorganic anions, such as nitrates and chloride [40]. These species are known to act as scavengers of hydroxyl radicals, thereby limiting their availability and contributing to the different photocatalytic behaviour observed between the two matrices.

Regarding hydrogen peroxide production (Fig. 7), similar H_2O_2 generation profiles were observed in Milli-Q water and WWE; however, in WWE the maximum H_2O_2 concentration reached after 1 h was approximately 14% lower than that measured in Milli-Q water. While the maximum concentration produced was similar in both actual water samples, the time evolution of H_2O_2 differed markedly between the two matrices. In WWE, the maximum H_2O_2 concentration was reached after only 1 h, followed by a marked decrease; in contrast, in FFW the maximum concentration was reached after 4 h, and upon further

Fig. 7. H_2O_2 production profiles with $\text{P}(5)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ in real matrices spiked under irradiation $\lambda > 340$ nm. Inset: kinetic constants of CBZ degradation in the spiked real matrices compared to MilliQ water.

irradiation, a limited decrease of approximately 16% was recorded. It can therefore be concluded that the matrix exhibiting the fastest H_2O_2 formation is also the one in which CBZ disappears most rapidly. This may be attributed to the differing composition of the two matrices.

3.7. Testing under UVC-light

Finally, we tested under UVC light the material that has shown good performance in terms of hydrogen peroxide production, namely $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$. With an absorption maximum at about 254 nm (UV-C range), H_2O_2 can generate, by photolytic decomposition, OH radicals able to attack organic substrates, promoting their degradation. The objective was to evaluate whether the heterogeneous photocatalytic process could be enhanced by the in-situ photolysis of H_2O_2 generated by the catalyst itself.

As it can be seen in Fig. 8, photolysis with UVC light resulted in limited CBZ photodegradation, reaching only 20% removal after 1 h. The disappearance of CBZ was followed also in presence of $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ and with the addition of $150\mu\text{M}$ of H_2O_2 . This concentration was chosen because it corresponds to the highest concentration produced in solution in the presence of CBZ with $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ under UV light. Combining H_2O_2 with $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ results in a significant enhancement of degradation efficiency, leading to the complete degradation of CBZ in less than 1 h, thus suggesting a synergistic effect between the two systems. This enhancement can be attributed to the increased generation of hydroxyl radicals through the interaction of electrons with H_2O_2 , forming hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and hydroxide ions (OH^-). The resulting hydroxide ions can subsequently react with photogenerated holes to produce additional $\cdot\text{OH}$, thereby amplifying the oxidative capacity of the system.

The formation of reactive oxygen species during the photocatalytic process was further investigated by EPR spectroscopy (Fig. S10). The spectra indicate the generation of radical intermediates under irradiation, which are responsible for both CBZ degradation and H_2O_2 production. In particular, the detected signals are consistent with the formation of superoxide radicals ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) and hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$). The $\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ species are generated via the reduction of dissolved oxygen by photogenerated electrons and play a key role in the formation of H_2O_2 through subsequent protonation and reduction steps. On the other hand, $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals are formed through oxidation pathways involving photogenerated holes and are highly reactive species responsible for the degradation of CBZ. These results are consistent with previous studies reporting that the interplay between reduction ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$ formation) and oxidation ($\bullet\text{OH}$ generation) pathways governs the efficiency of

Fig. 8. Carbamazepine degradation curves by $\text{P}(50)\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ under UV-C irradiation.

photocatalytic systems for simultaneous pollutant degradation and H₂O₂ production. Although detailed scavenger experiments were not performed, the EPR results provide direct evidence of radical formation and support the proposed mechanism [41–43].

Under UV-C irradiation, the EPR spin-trapping experiments further showed that the combination of hydrogen peroxide with the photocatalyst leads to the decomposition of H₂O₂. Irradiation in the presence of only photocatalyst or only hydrogen peroxide does not lead to the formation of OH radicals. The formation of OH radicals is observed in higher amount when the photocatalyst has been irradiated with H₂O₂. Irradiation with photocatalyst and CBZ leads to a lower amount of OH radicals while an intermediate situation is observed in the case of the mixture of the three components: in this case part of the generated OH radicals generated are scavenged by CBZ thus indicating enhanced oxidative activity in the system.

4. Conclusions

Phosphorus doping emerges as an effective strategy to modulate the structural and electronic properties of g-C₃N₄, with clear implications for its photocatalytic performance. Low dopant levels, particularly 5 mmol, preserve the structural order and melem-related features of the polymeric network while enabling favourable electronic adjustments that enhance both CBZ degradation and oxidant generation. Among all materials, P(5)C₃N₄ displayed the highest activity, whereas higher P loadings induced structural disorder and diminished photocatalytic efficiency.

The performance of P(5)C₃N₄ was further assessed in two real spiked water matrices, confirming its robustness under environmentally relevant scenarios. Although both the effluent wastewater (WWE) and fish-farm water (FFW) samples led to reduced degradation rates, the catalyst retained appreciable photocatalytic efficiency. Differences in H₂O₂ profiles between the two matrices highlight the significant influence of matrix composition on reactive species dynamics.

In addition, P(50)C₃N₄, selected for exhibiting the highest H₂O₂ generation among the synthesized materials, was tested under UVC light to assess whether in-situ photolysis of the peroxide could enhance CBZ degradation. While UVC irradiation alone achieved limited CBZ removal (~20% in 1 h), combining the catalyst with H₂O₂ led to complete degradation within one hour, demonstrating a synergistic effect. This enhancement is attributed to increased ·OH radical formation via electron-H₂O₂ interactions and hole-mediated reactions, amplifying the system's oxidative capacity.

In particular, lightly P-doped g-C₃N₄ offers an optimal balance between oxidant production enhancement and the enhancement of degradative capacities, positioning it as a promising material for advanced oxidation processes and hybrid Fenton-like systems.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jece.2026.122659](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2026.122659).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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